

Online Purchase preferences of residents of Delhi NCR

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Introduction

In the contemporary era of digitalization and globalization, online shopping has emerged as a prominent facet of consumer behavior, revolutionizing traditional retail paradigms. With the advent of e-commerce platforms (Chen *et al.* 2020) and the proliferation of internet accessibility, consumers are presented with a myriad of options (Hwang & Jeong, 2014) to fulfill their purchasing needs conveniently from the comfort of their homes. This shift towards online shopping has not only transformed the retail landscape (Li *et al.*, 2020; Scholz *et al.* 2019) but has also reshaped consumer preferences and purchasing patterns.

This research paper delves into the online purchase preferences of residents in the National Capital Region (NCR), with a specific focus on Delhi and its surrounding areas. The NCR, comprising Delhi along with satellite cities such as Gurugram, Noida, and Faridabad, represents one of the largest urban agglomerations in India, characterized by diverse demographics, socio-economic backgrounds, and consumer behaviors. Understanding the online buying preferences (Lig *et al.* 2010) of residents in this dynamic region holds significant implications for businesses, policymakers, and marketers seeking to capitalize on the burgeoning e-commerce market (Guo *et al.* 2023, Goyal *et al.* 2017).

The primary objective of this study is to analyze the relationship between demographic factors, namely gender, age, educational qualification, and income, and their influence on online purchasing preferences among residents of Delhi NCR. By examining these factors in conjunction with consumer behavior, this research aims to provide valuable insights into the underlying determinants driving online shopping preferences in the region.

This research endeavor seeks to contribute to the existing body of knowledge surrounding consumer behavior in the context of online shopping (Hwang & Jeong, 2014; Lin & Lu, 2011),

with a specific focus on the residents of Delhi NCR. By examining the interplay between demographic factors and online purchasing preferences, this study endeavors to provide actionable insights for businesses, marketers, and policymakers navigating the ever-evolving landscape of e-commerce.

Need of the Study

The exponential growth of e-commerce platforms and the increasing digitization of retail services have reshaped the way consumers shop. However, despite the burgeoning popularity of online shopping, there is a paucity of comprehensive studies focusing on the specific preferences and patterns of online purchases among residents of Delhi NCR. Understanding the factors that influence consumers' online buying behavior in this region is essential for businesses to tailor their marketing strategies, enhance customer experiences, and drive sales growth.

Research Objectives

The primary objective of this research paper is to analyze the online purchase preferences of residents in the Delhi National Capital Region across various demographic segments. Specifically, the study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. To examine the relationship between gender and online buying preferences among residents of Delhi NCR.
2. To assess how age influences the purchase preferences of respondents in online shopping.
3. To analyze the impact of educational qualifications on the online buying behavior of consumers in the region.
4. To investigate the correlation between income levels and online purchase preferences among residents of Delhi NCR.

Research Methodology

This research adopts a quantitative approach to gather and analyze data pertaining to the online purchase preferences of residents in the Delhi NCR region on a sample of 300. However, data that could be put for analysis was only for 291 sets as others were either incomplete or not upto the mark. A structured questionnaire survey was administered to a sample of respondents,

encompassing various demographic characteristics such as gender, age, educational qualification, and income level. The data collected were analyzed using statistical technique of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to identify patterns and relationships between demographic variables and online buying preferences.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this research paper hold significant implications for both academia and industry. From an academic perspective, the study contributes to the existing literature on consumer behavior and e-commerce by providing insights into the specific preferences of residents in the Delhi NCR region. Furthermore, the research offers valuable empirical evidence that can serve as a foundation for future studies in this field.

From a practical standpoint, the insights derived from this study will be invaluable for businesses operating in the e-commerce sector. By understanding the online purchase preferences of consumers in Delhi NCR, companies can tailor their marketing strategies, optimize product offerings, and enhance customer experiences to better cater to the needs and preferences of their target audience.

In conclusion, this research paper seeks to bridge the gap in existing literature by providing a comprehensive analysis of the online purchase preferences of residents in the Delhi NCR region. By examining the influence of demographic factors such as gender, age, educational qualification, and income level on online buying behavior, the study aims to offer valuable insights that can inform strategic decision-making and drive business growth in the dynamic e-commerce landscape.

Data Analysis & Interpretation

Gender and Online buying preference

The table provides both the average and dispersion of purchase preferences for male and female respondents. It is apparent from the table that gender plays a substantial role in shaping respondents' purchase preferences. To assess the significance of the variance between male and female respondents' purchase preferences, a t-test was performed. The

ANOVA analysis revealed that electronics exhibit the most pronounced disparity among male and female respondents, with the highest F-value of 21.959***. Additionally, the ANOVA value for beauty care, at 12.185***, indicates a notable distinction between the genders' preferences, although it is lower compared to electronics. Thus, it is evident that electronics display the most significant divergence among various purchase preferences.

Table : Gender and Online buying preference

Background	Male (n=158)		Female (n=133)		f-Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Electronics	3.63	2.52	2.61	2.55	21.949***
Apparels	3.75	2.52	3.57	2.64	0.829
Grocery	3.00	2.52	2.57	2.47	3.699**
Home Care	2.91	2.44	3.02	2.36	0.195
Baby Care	2.38	2.56	2.06	2.46	2.145
Beauty Care	2.95	2.46	3.74	2.56	12.185***
Pharmacy	2.52	2.62	2.01	2.52	5.163**

*** Significant at 1 % level, ** Significant at 5 % level

Age and Purchase Preference of the respondents

The table presents data concerning the average and standard deviation across various age brackets regarding purchase preferences, as well as the notable variances between them. The data indicates that respondents' preferences vary according to their age. An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was employed to examine these discrepancies. The ANOVA statistic of 8.314*** indicates a substantial distinction between respondents' ages and their inclination towards baby care products, suggesting a considerable variance in mean values across age groups. Similarly, for electronics, the mean values and ANOVA of 6.697*** across

different age brackets reveal a significant distinction. Conversely, the ANOVA statistic of 3.918**** for apparel purchase preferences suggests a comparatively minor difference in significance.

Table : Age and Purchase preference of the respondents

	Age Group	N	Mean	SD	F -Value
Electronics	16-22 Years	74	2.86	2.68	6.697****
	22-28 Years	78	3.77	2.59	
	28-40Years	71	4.24	2.43	
	>40 Years	68	3.76	2.45	
Apparels	16-22 Years	74	2.46	2.56	3.918****
	22-28 Years	78	3.21	2.61	
	28-40Years	71	3.36	2.42	
	>40 Years	68	3.43	2.71	
Grocery	16-22 Years	74	2.05	2.28	6.523****
	22-28 Years	78	2.79	2.42	
	28-40Years	71	3.37	2.53	
	>40 Years	68	2.94	2.61	
Home Care	16-22 Years	74	2.35	2.32	4.275****
	22-28 Years	78	2.98	2.25	
	28-40Years	71	3.35	2.44	
	>40 Years	68	3.17	2.59	
Baby Care	16-22 Years	74	1.47	2.14	8.314****
	22-28 Years	78	2.13	2.33	
	28-40Years	71	3.00	2.73	

	>40 Years	68	2.33	2.71	
Beauty Care	16-22 Years	74	2.97	2.44	2.276**
	22-28 Years	78	3.65	2.59	
	28-40Years	71	3.58	2.56	
	>40 Years	68	3.14	2.56	
Pharmacy	16-22 Years	74	1.58	2.26	4.593****
	22-28 Years	78	2.23	2.48	
	28-40Years	71	2.56	2.66	
	>40 Years	68	2.64	2.86	

*** Significant at 1 % level, ** Significant at 5 % level

Educational Qualification and Online buying preference

The relationship between respondents' educational qualifications and their purchase preferences is detailed in Table . This table presents the mean, standard deviation, and f-value of respondents' responses across varying educational backgrounds. The computed values indicate a notable distinction in purchase preferences based on educational qualifications. An analysis of variance (ANOVA) has been conducted to compare different purchase preferences among respondents with varying educational backgrounds. The highest ANOVA value (9.757****) underscores a significant variation in electronics purchases across different levels of education. Similarly, notable differences are observed in baby care (8.997****), pharmacy (8.589****), grocery (8.386****), and home care (7.024****) purchases among respondents with differing educational levels. However, in the case of beauty care, while still significant, the ANOVA value (4.989****) is slightly lower compared to other purchase preferences.

Table : Educational Qualification an Online buying preference

					ANOVA F-Value
		N	Mean	SD	
Apparels	<plus two	23	3.32	2.67	9.757***
	UG	59	2.49	2.52	
	Graduate	99	3.87	2.61	
	PG	26	4.97	2.13	
	>PG	84	3.88	2.42	
Electronics	<plus two	23	3.09	2.83	6.090***
	UG	59	2.18	2.42	
	Graduate	99	3.05	2.59	
	PG	26	4.05	2.44	
	>PG	84	3.52	2.54	
Grocery	<plus two	23	2.69	2.43	8.386***
	UG	59	1.87	2.30	
	Graduate	99	2.80	2.48	
	PG	26	4.29	2.28	
	>PG	84	2.94	2.50	
Home Care	<plus two	23	3.07	2.36	7.024***
	UG	59	2.13	2.26	
	Graduate	99	3.04	2.49	
	PG	26	4.29	2.15	
	>PG	84	2.98	2.34	
Baby Care	<plus two	23	2.59	2.66	8.997***
	UG	59	1.35	2.03	
	Graduate	99	2.19	2.56	
	PG	26	3.88	2.53	
	>PG	84	2.24	2.53	
Personal or Beauty Care	<plus two	23	2.99	2.29	4.989***
	UG	59	2.69	2.32	

	Graduate	99	3.46	2.61	
	PG	26	4.59	2.53	
	>PG	84	3.34	2.55	
Pharmacy	<plus two	23	2.29	2.80	8.589 ^{***}
	UG	59	1.44	2.10	
	Graduate	99	2.31	2.60	
	PG	26	4.01	2.70	
	>PG	84	2.14	2.55	

^{***} Significant at 1 % level

Income and Online buying preference

The table provides the average, standard deviation, and ANOVA F-value for the relationship between income level and respondents' purchase preferences. The findings reveal that, with the exception of baby care purchase preference, all other categories exhibit a notably significant disparity. Specifically, the ANOVA values for apparel (16.257), grocery (14.083), electronics (14.021), beauty care (8.613), pharmacy (8.473), and homecare (7.259) highlight a substantial difference in respondents' purchase preferences based on their income levels.

Table : Income and Online buying preference

		N	Mean	SD	ANOV A F- Value
Apparels	< ₹25K PM	135	2.90	2.50	16.267
	₹25K-75K PM	80	4.05	2.64	
	₹75K-100K PM	52	4.22	2.31	
	>100K PM	25	5.24	2.10	
Electronics	< ₹25K PM	135	2.49	2.52	13.031
	₹25K-75K PM	80	3.27	2.69	

	₹75K-100K PM	52	3.66	2.34	
	>100K PM	25	4.76	2.24	
Grocery	< ₹25K PM	135	2.17	2.28	14.093
	₹25K-75K PM	80	3.03	2.61	
	₹75K-100K PM	52	3.12	2.50	
	>100K PM	25	4.54	2.21	
Home-Care	< ₹25K PM	135	2.53	2.28	7.269
	₹25K-75K PM	80	3.18	2.54	
	₹75K-100K PM	52	3.13	2.32	
	>100K PM	25	4.19	2.43	
Baby Care	< ₹25K PM	135	1.95	2.40	3.913
	₹25K-75K PM	80	2.11	2.51	
	₹75K-100K PM	52	2.64	2.65	
	>100K PM	25	3.15	2.82	
Beauty Care	< ₹25K PM	135	2.80	2.43	8.623
	₹25K-75K PM	80	3.80	2.60	
	₹75K-100K PM	52	3.47	2.44	
	>100K PM	25	4.49	2.58	
	Total	135	1.72	2.38	
Pharmacy	< ₹25K PM	80	2.47	2.65	8.483
	₹25K-75K PM	52	2.60	2.70	
	₹75K-100K PM	25	3.58	2.67	
	>100K PM	135	2.90	2.50	

Findings

The examination of purchase preferences among respondents based on various demographic factors offers a nuanced understanding of consumer behavior within the context of different socio-economic and personal backgrounds. Gender emerges as a significant determinant, with the analysis revealing notable disparities between male and female respondents. Particularly striking is the substantial difference observed in electronics purchases. Similarly, although to a slightly lesser extent, beauty care purchases also exhibit significant differences between genders.

Age, another critical demographic variable, plays a discernible role in shaping purchase preferences. The analysis highlights significant variations across age groups, with certain product categories demonstrating more pronounced differences than others. For instance, baby care products show a substantial discrepancy across different age brackets. In parallel, electronics purchases also display notable differences among respondents of varying ages. Conversely, the variance in apparel purchase preferences appears comparatively minor, with an ANOVA of 3.918***, suggesting a more consistent trend across age groups.

Educational qualification emerges as another influential factor, with distinct patterns observed in purchase preferences among respondents with different educational backgrounds. Notably, electronics purchases exhibit significant variation across educational levels. This suggests that educational attainment significantly influences preferences in this product category. Similar trends are observed in other product categories, such as baby care, pharmacy, grocery, and home care, albeit to varying degrees. However, the ANOVA value for beauty care, while still significant at 4.989***, indicates a slightly lower level of disparity compared to other purchase preferences.

Finally, income level emerges as a critical determinant of purchase preferences, with substantial variations observed across different income brackets. Except for baby care, all other product categories demonstrate notable disparities based on respondents' income levels. Apparel, grocery, electronics, beauty care, pharmacy, and home care purchases all exhibit significant differences, as evidenced by their respective ANOVA values. This underscores the importance of income as a key factor shaping consumer behavior in the context of online purchasing.

Implications of the study

The findings from the research on purchase preferences among respondents based on various demographic factors offer several implications for businesses, marketers, and policymakers:

1. Businesses can tailor their marketing strategies and product offerings to cater to the specific preferences of male and female consumers. For instance, the substantial difference observed in electronics purchases suggests the need for gender-specific marketing campaigns or product designs to appeal to different segments of the market.
2. Understanding the significant variations in purchase preferences across different age groups can guide businesses in developing age-appropriate products and marketing campaigns. For example, the substantial discrepancy observed in baby care products across age brackets highlights the importance of offering diverse product ranges to cater to varying needs and preferences.
3. The significant variation in purchase preferences across educational levels emphasizes the influence of educational attainment on consumer behavior. Marketers can segment their target audience based on educational qualifications and tailor their messaging and product offerings accordingly.
4. The substantial variations in purchase preferences based on income levels underscore the importance of pricing strategies and product offerings that cater to different income brackets. Businesses can consider offering a range of products at varying price points to appeal to a diverse customer base and maximize sales potential.
5. Policymakers can use the insights from the research to design interventions aimed at promoting socio-economic equity and access to essential products and services. Understanding how income influences purchase preferences can inform policies related to affordability, access, and consumer welfare.

The research findings provide valuable insights into the complex interplay between demographic factors and consumer behavior in the context of online purchasing. Businesses, marketers, and policymakers can leverage these insights to develop more effective strategies and interventions

that meet the diverse needs and preferences of consumers across different socio-economic and personal backgrounds.

CONCLUSIONS

The study delves into understanding of consumer behavior by examining purchase preferences across various demographic factors. Gender disparities are evident, notably in electronics and beauty care purchases, underscoring the need for tailored marketing strategies. Age plays a pivotal role, with significant variations observed across product categories, particularly in baby care and electronics. Educational qualifications also shape preferences, with electronics exhibiting substantial variation among educational levels. Income level emerges as a key determinant, impacting purchase preferences across all categories except baby care. These findings offer businesses and marketers invaluable insights into developing targeted strategies that resonate with diverse consumer segments, from gender-specific marketing campaigns to age-appropriate product offerings. Moreover, policymakers can leverage these insights to design interventions promoting socio-economic equity and access to essential goods and services, ultimately enhancing consumer welfare.

In conclusion, the research illuminates the intricate dynamics between demographic factors and online purchase preferences, empowering stakeholders to navigate the evolving landscape of consumer behavior. By leveraging these insights, businesses can refine their marketing approaches, optimize product offerings, and tailor pricing strategies to better meet the needs and preferences of diverse consumer segments. Meanwhile, policymakers can utilize these findings to formulate policies aimed at fostering socio-economic inclusivity and ensuring equitable access to essential products. Collectively, these efforts contribute to enhancing consumer satisfaction and fostering a more vibrant and inclusive online marketplace.

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